

An Investigation of Serum Vitamin B12 Levels and Their Correlation With BMI, Waist-Hip Ratio, and Glycaemic Markers in Diabetic Patients

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Abstract

Background: An increasing number of individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), especially those who have been taking metformin for a long time, are being found to have low levels of vitamin B12. Lack of this important micronutrient may affect blood sugar control and body composition, but its relationship with important measures like Body Mass Index (BMI), Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR), fasting, and Glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1c). **Objective:** To assess the vitamin B12 levels in the blood of patients with T2DM and correlate to BMI, WHR, and biochemical parameters of glycaemic indicators levels. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was done with 200 patients age group (31-80yrs) with T2DM. The body measurements (weight, height, waist and hip circumference), serum vitamin B12 levels, and HbA1c levels were assessed. SPSS software was used to calculate correlation and group comparison analyses. **Results:** The study revealed no significant correlation between serum vitamin B12 concentrations and anthropometric measures, including Body Mass Index (BMI) ($r = 0.011$, $p = 0.881$) or Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR) ($r = -0.068$, $p = 0.338$), indicating that body weight and fat distribution do not markedly affect B12 status in diabetic individuals. Vitamin B12 levels exhibited a modest yet statistically significant inverse correlation with fasting blood glucose ($r = -0.144$, $p = 0.042$), postprandial glucose ($r = -0.171$, $p = 0.015$), and HbA1c ($r = -0.152$, $p = 0.032$), suggesting a potential association between diminished B12 levels and impaired glycaemic control. **Conclusion:** A significant number of people with diabetes have difficulty obtaining enough vitamin B12, and this is linked to bad effects on body measurements and blood sugar levels. It is important to check B12 levels regularly, especially in overweight and poorly controlled diabetic patients, so that early action can be taken and metabolic management can be improved.

Keywords

Vitamin B12, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, BMI, WHR, HbA1c, Metformin, Glycaemic Control.

Introduction

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) has emerged as a significant worldwide health concern, with rising prevalence in both developed and developing countries. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF, 2021) reported that around 537 million persons globally had diabetes in 2021, with projections indicating an increase to 643 million by 2030. India, specifically, carries a substantial cost, with around 77 million individuals impacted (IDF, 2021). Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is linked not just to hyperglycaemia but also to chronic consequences that might impact many organ systems. A thorough comprehension of dietary, biochemical, and anthropometric aspects in diabetic patients is essential for more successful disease management.

Vitamin B12 (cobalamin) has lately garnered interest as a nutritional biomarker due to its involvement in multiple metabolic pathways. Vitamin B12 is a water-soluble vitamin essential for DNA synthesis, erythropoiesis, and neurological function. It also contributes to the metabolism of fatty acids and amino acids, serving as a cofactor for enzymes engaged in energy synthesis (O'Leary & Samman, 2010). A deficiency in vitamin B12 can lead to hematologic and neuropsychiatric disorders and may complicate diabetes management by simulating or intensifying symptoms of diabetic neuropathy.

Vitamin B12 deficiency is commonly reported in diabetic individuals, particularly those undergoing prolonged metformin treatment. Metformin, the primary treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus, has been documented to disrupt vitamin B12 absorption via modifying calcium-dependent membrane activity in the ileum (de Jager et al., 2010). A meta-analysis by Chapman et al. (2016) revealed that prolonged metformin administration significantly decreased serum vitamin B12 levels and heightened the risk of insufficiency. Reduced B12 levels in diabetic individuals may result in peripheral neuropathy, hence exacerbating the clinical scenario and diminishing patients' quality of life. Recent years have seen an increasing interest in the correlation between B12 status and various diabetic indicators, including glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c), body mass index (BMI), and waist-hip ratio (WHR). Nevertheless, literature presents contradictory results, with certain research

demonstrating an inverse relationship between B12 and HbA1c, whereas others suggest an absence of a definitive correlation (Margalit et al., 2010; Ting et al., 2006).

Anthropometric indicators, including BMI and WHR, are critical metrics for assessing obesity and fat distribution, recognised as risk factors for insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Obesity is closely associated with chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and modified adipokine production, all of which might affect glucose metabolism (Guh et al., 2009). Central obesity, as shown by an elevated waist-to-hip ratio (WHR), shows a more robust correlation with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular risk than general obesity assessed solely by body mass index (BMI).

Recent studies indicate that micronutrient imbalances, particularly B12 deficiency, may be more common among overweight or obese individuals due to suboptimal diet quality and reduced consumption of animal products, especially within vegetarian populations prevalent in India (Khanduri & Sharma, 2007). Moreover, metabolic alterations associated with obesity may influence vitamin absorption and metabolism, rendering the investigation of B12 status across BMI and WHR categories very pertinent.

HbA1c indicates average blood glucose levels over the past 2–3 months and serves as a vital indicator for assessing glycaemic management in diabetes. Inadequate glycaemic regulation (elevated HbA1c levels) has been linked to microvascular and macrovascular problems. Certain studies have investigated the relationship between serum vitamin B12 and HbA1c levels, indicating that B12 deficiency may disrupt glucose metabolism or signify inadequate nutritional status, potentially exacerbating glycaemic outcomes (Reinstatler et al., 2012). The direction and significance of this relationship remain contentious. Despite the established biochemical and physiological functions of vitamin B12, its status and correlations with anthropometric and glycaemic indices are frequently underexplored in diabetic communities, particularly in resource-limited environments. The primarily vegetarian dietary habits in India, coupled with the extensive use of metformin, render Indian diabetic populations especially vulnerable to vitamin B12 insufficiency.

This study seeks to address the deficiency by assessing serum vitamin B12 levels in diabetes patients and their correlation with BMI, WHR, and glycaemic markers. Comprehending these linkages can facilitate the formulation of tailored dietary therapies and enhance monitoring techniques.

Objective of study

1. To estimate the serum vitamin B12 levels among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.
2. To evaluate the association of serum vitamin B12 levels with anthropometric and glycaemic indicators in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Review of Literature

Obesity, particularly central obesity, is a recognised risk factor for insulin resistance and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Anthropometric metrics such as BMI and WHR are frequently employed to evaluate overall and abdominal fatness. Research indicates a potential association between obesity and micronutrient deficiencies, such as B12, attributed to inadequate dietary practices and impaired absorption (Khanduri & Sharma, 2007). Pinhas-Hamiel et al. (2006) indicated that obese persons, despite excessive calorie consumption, frequently exhibit shortages in vital micronutrients, particularly B12. This contradiction can be ascribed to the intake of energy-dense yet nutrient-deficient foods. A cross-sectional study conducted by Kaptan et al. (2020) demonstrated that overweight and obese diabetic individuals exhibited markedly decreased vitamin B12 levels in comparison to their normal-weight counterparts. Furthermore, waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) has been progressively recognized as a superior predictor of metabolic problems compared to body mass index (BMI) alone, particularly in South Asian populations (Misra et al., 2009). Nevertheless, few studies have investigated the correlation between WHR and vitamin B12, rendering it a significant subject for inquiry.

HbA1c is a crucial clinical indicator utilized to evaluate long-term glycaemic regulation. Certain research has investigated the relationship between vitamin B12 level and glycaemic management, or the inverse. Margalit et al. (2010) identified an unfavourable correlation between serum B12 concentrations and HbA1c levels in newly diagnosed diabetes patients, indicating that inadequate vitamin status may impair glycaemic regulation. In contrast, research conducted by Kibirige et al. (2014) revealed no significant link between B12 levels and HbA1c, suggesting that the relationship may be affected by confounding variables such as nutrition, medication, and comorbidities. Consequently, additional study is necessary to elucidate the characteristics of this connection across other groups.

In India, vegetarian diets and prevalent metformin usage exacerbate the risk of vitamin B12 insufficiency in diabetic persons. A study by Deshmukh et al. (2015) in a tertiary hospital in Maharashtra indicated that almost 40% of T2DM patients exhibited subclinical or overt vitamin B12 insufficiency. Kannan and Karalliedde (2020) observed that Indian diabetic patients who had been on metformin for more than five years exhibited a markedly greater incidence of peripheral neuropathy, along with diminished serum B12 levels. These findings emphasize the significance of regular screening and nutritional counselling in Indian healthcare environments. A deficit in vitamin B12 can aggravate pre-existing diabetes problems, especially peripheral neuropathy, a prevalent and debilitating consequence of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). Subramaniam et al. (2014) established a notable correlation between diminished B12 levels and elevated Michigan

Neuropathy Screening Instrument (MNSI) scores in patients on metformin treatment. B12 deficiency-induced neuropathy frequently resembles diabetic neuropathy, resulting in possible misdiagnosis and postponed treatment.

Furthermore, research by Moore et al. (2012) has associated low B12 levels with cognitive deterioration and depression in elderly diabetic individuals, indicating that sufficient vitamin B12 status is crucial for preserving general neurological and psychological well-being in diabetes management. Although numerous studies have individually investigated the relationship between vitamin B12 and either glycaemic management or anthropometric indices, less research has assessed all these parameters collectively within a complete framework. Moreover, data relevant to the Indian population particularly for BMI, WHR, glycaemic indicators, and vitamin B12 status collectively are scarce. Additionally, there is an absence of studies assessing gender-based or age-stratified disparities in these correlations, which could yield insights for targeted interventions.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional, observational study conducted on patients diagnosed with Type 2 diabetes mellitus. The research was conducted in a tertiary care hospital named Sir Sunder Lal Hospital BHU, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India, subsequent to obtaining ethical permission from the ethics committee. The committee's registration number is ECR/226/Indt/UP/2014/RR-22, dated January 4, 2022, and it is registered under Rule 122DD of the Drugs & Cosmetics Rule 1945.

Two hundred diabetes patients were recruited utilising a purposive sampling method. Inclusion criteria encompassed adult patients aged 30 years and older, diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus for a minimum duration of 6 months. Individuals having a documented history of chronic gastrointestinal disorders, those receiving vitamin B12 supplementation, or those with illnesses that influence vitamin B12 levels (such as pernicious anaemia or chronic alcohol consumption) were excluded. Data were gathered with a systematic interview protocol and clinical assessment. The questionnaire comprised sections on: Socio-demographic data (age, gender, marital status, residential area, educational attainment, and eating practices). Clinical information, encompassing the duration of diabetes and current pharmacological treatments. Data collection started after granted the consent of the patients. The Body Mass Index (BMI) was computed utilizing the formula $\text{weight (kg)} / \text{height}^2 \text{ (m}^2\text{)}$ and classified in accordance with WHO guidelines. The Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR) was assessed using a non-elastic tape; waist circumference was recorded at the midpoint between the lower edge of the last palpable rib and the superior aspect of the iliac crest, while hip circumference was measured at the broadest part of the buttocks. WHR was then classified according to WHO gender-specific thresholds. Biochemical parameters were obtained from the patients reports given by the certified laboratories.

Statistical Examination: Data were inputted and analysed utilising SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software version 25. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were employed to summarise the data. The relationship between Vitamin B12 levels and categorical variables was evaluated using the Chi-square test. Pearson correlation coefficients were computed to evaluate the association between blood Vitamin B12 and continuous variables, including BMI, WHR, FBG, PPBG, and HbA1c. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Result and Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate serum Vitamin B12 levels and their correlation with BMI, Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR), and glycaemic markers (Fasting Blood Glucose, Postprandial Glucose, and HbA1c) in individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Two hundred people with diabetes participated in the study. The findings are displayed in a tabular format and encompass descriptive statistics, frequency distributions, and correlation analysis.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of socio-demographic profile.

Sociodemographic Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
31-40	37	18.5
41-50	51	25.5
51-60	71	35.5
61-70	34	7.0
71-80	7	3.5
Gender		
Male	93	46.5
Female	107	53.5
Marital Status		
Married	190	95
Unmarried	1	0.5
Divorced/ Widow	9	4.5
Area of Residence		
Urban	64	32
Rural	77	38.5
Semi Urban	59	29.5
Qualification		
Professional Degree	3	1.5
Graduation/ Post Graduation	59	29.5
12/ Diploma	41	20.5
High School	31	15.5
Middle School	26	13.0
Primary School	21	10.5
Illiterate	19	9.5
Food Habit		
Vegetarian	124	62
Eggetarian	17	8.5
Non vegetarian	59	29.5

Table 1 shows the current study comprised 200 diabetes patients, with a greater proportion of females (53.5%) than males (46.5%). This gender distribution corresponds with prior studies suggesting an increasing incidence of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) among women in India, likely attributable to sedentary lifestyles and hormonal factors (Anjana et al., 2011). The age distribution indicated that the predominant group of participants (35.5%) was aged 51–60 years, followed by 25.5% in the 41–50 age range and 18.5% in the 31–40 age bracket. This data aligns with epidemiological trends indicating that T2DM is predominantly diagnosed in middle-aged people, typically between the ages of 45 and 60 (Ramachandran et al., 2008). Concerning marital status, 95% of participants were married, 0.5% were unmarried, and 4.5% were either divorced or widowed. The significant proportion of married persons illustrates the demographic characteristics of adult populations in India and may be pertinent to the social support systems influencing diabetes management.

The predominant group of participants resided in rural areas (38.5%), followed by urban (32%) and semi-urban (29.5%) regions. This distribution highlights the growing prevalence of diabetes among rural populations, which were previously deemed at lower risk but are now more impacted by evolving lifestyles and dietary practices (Misra & Khurana, 2011). The gap in diabetes prevalence between urban and rural areas is diminishing, highlighting the necessity for targeted public health initiatives in non-urban locales. Educational qualifications indicated that 29.5% of participants were graduates or postgraduates, while 20.5% had completed 12th grade or obtained a diploma. A considerable percentage possessed merely fundamental education 13% had attended middle school, 10.5% had completed primary school, and 9.5% were illiterate. Education significantly influences diabetes awareness and self-care habits; lower educational attainment correlates with inferior glycaemic control and increased complications (Shrivastava et al., 2013). The majority of participants (62%) were vegetarians, followed by 29.5% non-vegetarians and 8.5% eggetarians. This reflects the dietary patterns of numerous Indian populations, especially those with cultural or religious tendencies towards vegetarianism. Research indicates that non-vegetarian diets, especially those

rich in saturated fats, may lead to insulin resistance, while plant-based diets could offer protection against type 2 diabetes mellitus and its comorbidities (Satiya et al., 2016).

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of the Vitamin B12 Count.

Vitamin B12 (pg/ml)	Frequency (n)	Percentage(%)
<191	61	30.5
191-350	52	26
>350	87	43.5

Table 2 shows the serum vitamin B12 level among diabetes patients in the study, indicating that a substantial percentage (43.5%) had B12 levels over 350 pg/mL, signifying adequacy. A significant proportion of participants 30.5% exhibited vitamin B12 insufficiency, with serum concentrations falling below 191 pg/ml, whilst 26% presented with borderline levels (191–350 pg/ml). The findings raise therapeutic concerns as vitamin B12 deficiency is prevalent in persons with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, especially those on prolonged metformin medication, which hinders B12 absorption in the gastrointestinal tract (de Jager et al., 2010).

This study's findings on deficiency correspond with earlier results suggesting that 20%–30% of diabetic patients may have low or marginal B12 levels (Reinstatler et al., 2012). This dietary shortage may lead to haematological abnormalities and peripheral neuropathy, both prevalent and devastating consequences in diabetic populations. Consequently, regular assessment of vitamin B12 levels in diabetic individuals, particularly those on metformin, is essential to avert long-term problems and to provide prompt replenishment.

Table 3: Gender-wise frequency distribution of the subjects on the basis of their Body Mass Index.

BMI (kg/m ²)	Female		Male		Total		P Value
	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	
<18.5	3	2.8	1	1.07	4	2	0.049
18.5-24.5	19	17.8	14	15.05	33	16.5	
25-29.9	59	55.1	39	41.9	98	49	
>30	26	24.3	39	41.9	65	32.5	
Total	107	100	93	100	200	100	

F- Frequency; P- Percentage

Table 3 shows the gender-specific distribution of Body Mass Index (BMI) among individuals with diabetes that reveals significant disparities. Among female participants, the predominant proportion (55.1%) was categorized as overweight (BMI 25–29.9), whilst 24.3% were classified as obese (BMI >30). A marginally greater percentage of males (41.9%) were classified as obese in comparison to females, while 41.9% were also categorized as overweight. Only a small percentage of participants were underweight, with three females and one male falling below the BMI threshold of 18.5. The identified gender disparity in BMI distribution was statistically significant (p = 0.049), indicating that gender may affect body weight patterns in individuals with diabetes.

These findings align with prior research demonstrating that overweight and obesity are frequent in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) populations, exhibiting distinct gender patterns. Women, especially around middle age, frequently face an elevated risk of weight gain attributable to hormonal fluctuations, diminished physical activity, and nutritional influences (Misra et al., 2011). The elevated frequency of obesity among males in this study may indicate lifestyle-related characteristics, including central obesity, eating habits, and diminished metabolic flexibility, which are associated with an increased risk of diabetes (Després, 2012).

Body Mass Index (BMI) is a vital metric in diabetes care, since elevated adiposity, particularly visceral fat, is significantly correlated with insulin resistance and inadequate glycaemic control. Consequently, gender-specific therapies targeting weight management and lifestyle change may be crucial in the therapeutic management of T2DM.

Table 4: Gender-wise frequency distribution of the subjects on the basis of their Waist Hip Ratio.

BMI (kg/m ²)	Female		Male		Total		P Value
	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	

<18.5	3	2.8	1	1.07	4	2	0.049
18.5-24.5	19	17.8	14	15.05	33	16.5	
25-29.9	59	55.1	39	41.9	98	49	
>30	26	24.3	39	41.9	65	32.5	
Total	107	100	93	100	200	100	

F- Frequency; P- Percentage

Table 4 shows the gender-specific distribution of Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR) among diabetic patients that demonstrated substantial disparities between males and females ($p = 0.000$), signifying a statistically significant correlation between gender and adipose distribution patterns. A predominant proportion of both male and female participants (89%) had a waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) within the range of 0.80–0.90. Notably, 13 female subjects had a WHR below 0.80, in contrast to a single man, whilst 7 females and 1 male demonstrated a WHR beyond 0.90. This distribution indicates that central obesity, typically represented by an elevated WHR, may be more common among females with diabetes in this population.

Waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) is a crucial anthropometric metric indicative of abdominal fat deposition, significantly associated with insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular risk in persons with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (Yusuf et al., 2005). Women, although often possessing greater subcutaneous fat, may encounter heightened visceral fat buildup during and subsequent to menopause, hence elevating their metabolic risk. Conversely, men typically display a more centralised distribution of adipose tissue, even in their youth.

A high waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) is a more significant predictor of cardiovascular problems than body mass index (BMI) in diabetic patients; therefore, gender-specific screening and intervention techniques targeting abdominal obesity are crucial for preventing comorbidities and enhancing long-term outcomes (WHO, 2008).

Table 5: Gender-wise distribution of mean value of the biochemical parameters of the subjects.

BMI (kg/m ²)	Female		Male		Total		P Value
	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	F (n)	P (%)	
<18.5	3	2.8	1	1.07	4	2	0.049
18.5-24.5	19	17.8	14	15.05	33	16.5	
25-29.9	59	55.1	39	41.9	98	49	
>30	26	24.3	39	41.9	65	32.5	
Total	107	100	93	100	200	100	

Table 5 shows the examination of biochemical markers that indicated nuanced gender-specific variations among the diabetes subjects. The average fasting blood glucose (FBG) level was greater in females (208.5 ± 52.8 mg/dl) compared to males (196.4 ± 55.9 mg/dl), resulting in an overall mean of 202.8 ± 54.4 mg/dl. This signifies inadequate glycaemic control in both cohorts, with females exhibiting marginally inferior fasting glucose regulation. Analogous trends were noted for HbA1c, with females exhibiting a slightly elevated mean ($9.6 \pm 1.3\%$) relative to males ($9.4 \pm 1.3\%$), signifying persistent hyperglycaemia in both sexes. The observed values significantly exceed the suggested HbA1c target of <7% for diabetic individuals, indicating that the majority of subjects exhibited inadequate diabetes control. Increased HbA1c levels correlate with a heightened risk of microvascular and macrovascular problems (UKPDS, 1998).

In terms of postprandial blood glucose (PPBG), males exhibited somewhat elevated mean levels (285.7 ± 64.5 mg/dl) relative to females (279.4 ± 56.1 mg/dl), resulting in an overall average of 282.3 ± 60.1 mg/dL. Postprandial hyperglycaemia is a critical predictor of cardiovascular events in diabetic persons, especially within South Asian populations due to their high-carbohydrate dietary habits (IDF, 2019). In terms of serum Vitamin B12 concentrations, females exhibited considerably elevated mean levels (362.1 ± 147.4 pg/ml) compared to males (313.6 ± 173.3 pg/ml), resulting in an overall mean of 339.6 ± 161.4 pg/ml. Despite average readings for both genders being within the normal reference range, the comparatively lower B12 levels in males may necessitate further examination, particularly given the risk of B12 deficiency in diabetic patients undergoing metformin treatment. Prolonged B12 deficiency may result in neuropathy, exacerbating the neurological hazards already linked to diabetes (Reinstatler et al., 2012). These gender-specific differences underscore the necessity of personalised diabetes management approaches, encompassing consistent monitoring of glucose levels and nutritional status.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation Coefficients of Serum Vitamin B12 with BMI, WHR, and Glycemic Markers.

Variable	R value	P value
BMI	0.011	0.881
WHR	-0.068	0.338
FBG	-0.144	0.042
PPBG	-0.171	0.015
HbA1C	-0.152	0.032

Table 6 shows the correlation analysis between serum vitamin B12 levels and specific anthropometric and biochemical factors that reveals differing levels of relationship. No substantial connection was seen between Vitamin B12 and Body Mass Index (BMI) ($r = 0.011$, $p = 0.881$) or Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR) ($r = -0.068$, $p = 0.338$), suggesting that blood B12 levels were independent of body weight and fat distribution in this diabetic population. This indicates that obesity or central adiposity does not directly affect vitamin B12 status, a conclusion aligned with certain research that found no significant association between B12 insufficiency and BMI in diabetic populations (Chen et al., 2016).

A notable inverse connection was identified between serum vitamin B12 and fasting blood glucose (FBG) ($r = -0.144$, $p = 0.042$), postprandial glucose (PPBG) ($r = -0.171$, $p = 0.015$), and HbA1c ($r = -0.152$, $p = 0.032$). The negative correlations indicate that reduced vitamin B12 levels are moderately linked to inferior glycaemic management. The unfavourable correlation with HbA1c is notably significant, as it indicates chronic hyperglycaemia. This corroborates current data that vitamin B12 insufficiency, frequently caused by prolonged metformin usage in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, may hinder glucose metabolism or serve as an indicator of advanced disease (Bauman et al., 2000; Reinstatler et al., 2012). Although the correlations are statistically significant, the R-values are rather low, signifying weak yet meaningful relationships. These findings underscore the potential significance of vitamin B12 monitoring in holistic diabetes management and indicate that low B12 levels may coexist with inadequate glycaemic control, albeit without a causative relationship.

Conclusion

This study reveals that 30.5% of persons with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus have low vitamin B12 levels, while an additional 26% fall within the borderline range. No significant link was detected between serum vitamin B12 levels and anthropometric measures, such as BMI and WHR; nevertheless, a statistically significant inverse relationship was established between vitamin B12 and glycaemic parameters, including fasting blood glucose, postprandial glucose, and HbA1c. The results indicate that diminished vitamin B12 levels may correlate with suboptimal glycaemic management.

Due to the increasing prevalence of diabetes and the common administration of metformin, which is associated with vitamin B12 deficiency, routine assessment of B12 levels in diabetic patients is necessary. Timely detection and rectification of B12 deficiency may contribute to the prevention of consequences including neuropathy and cognitive impairment, thereby enhancing overall diabetes treatment. The gender and demographic disparities identified in this study underscore the necessity for personalised, focused nutritional and clinical interventions. Additional longitudinal and interventional studies are required to determine the causal association between vitamin B12 levels and glycaemic management, as well as to assess the advantages of B12 supplementation in enhancing metabolic outcomes in diabetic patients.

Abbreviations

- T2DM- Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
- BMI- Body Mass Index
- WHR- Waist Hip Ratio
- FBG- Fasting Blood Glucose
- PPBG-PostPrandialBloodGlucose
- HbA1C- Glycosylated Haemoglobin

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